

Prospects and Challenges of Managing Small Scale Manufacturing Businesses in Enugu East Senatorial Zone, Enugu State Nigeria

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Abstract: *The study analysed the prospects and challenges of managing small-scale manufacturing businesses in Enugu East Senatorial zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. The objectives were to examine the effect of poor planning on the management of small-scale manufacturing businesses, as well as investigate the effect of lack of finance on small-scale manufacturing enterprises. The study adopted the survey design. The population consists of thirty-nine (39) employees and management in specific businesses (vegetable oil and paint manufacturing) which were purposely selected and considered to be the sample. Primary data were used for this study and they were sourced through administration of structured questionnaire designed on a five-point Likert scale. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics while the hypotheses were tested with ordinal logistic regression using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The finding of the study showed that poor planning negatively affected the management of small-scale manufacturing business. Also, result revealed that lack of finance negatively affected small scale manufacturing enterprises. Thus, it was recommended that government and non- government organizations should endeavour to organize periodic training for small scale manufacturing business owners and managers as a way of mentoring them in proper management and improving their sustainability and contribution to the national economy. More so, financial institutions are encouraged to advance soft loan to small entrepreneurs at a low rate of interest for sustainable development of small enterprises into medium/large enterprises.*

Keywords: Small Business, Management, Finance, Enugu East Senatorial Zone

I. INTRODUCTION

Small scale enterprise is known as an important sector for economic development of any country. United Nations Development Programme, (1974) in Eze (2012) opines that Nigeria has from 1970 shown great interest in the progress of small scale entrepreneurship. The reasons for this include the great emphasis on self reliance as an approach in achieving sustainable development and the recognition of the contribution of small businesses to developmental objectives of a nation.

Small scale enterprises take up a place of pride in nearly every nation. This is because of the important role they play in the growth of national economies and transformation of any country (Ogbo and Agu, 2012).

The role of small manufacturing sub sector in national development was one of the major reasons the sub sector started receiving some support from the government after the Structural Adjustment Programme(SAP) and Second Tier Foreign Exchange Market (STEM) were introduced. This acknowledgement is based on the significant contribution small manufacturing enterprises could make in employment generation, poverty alleviation, increase in standard of living and Gross National Product (Leon, 2009).

The growth of the sub sector therefore is a very significant variable in the development plan of most economies, Nigeria inclusive.

Small manufacturing enterprises in Nigeria have not reached their zenith despite the various policies and programmes designed by the government and international institutions in the areas of advisory services, finance and training to support the sub sector to contribute to the growth of the economy through poverty reduction, generation of employment, raising standard of living and formation of substantial local capital (Ogbo and Agu, 2012). Many small manufacturing enterprises in Nigeria fold up before their fifth year, a smaller percentage die before their tenth year, and only five to ten percent survive (Agwu, 2014). This may be connected with poor business management which could

lead to failure of any business. Other constraints include harsh economic environment, difficulty in fulfilling conditions for assessing credit from financial institutions leading to under capitalization and high cost of business operation (Leon, 2009).

It is important to state that international organisations like World Bank, United Nations Industrial Development Organisation (UNIDO), European Investment Bank (EIB), *etc* are highly concerned in supporting and making small businesses robust and vibrant. Internally, there are some nongovernmental and governmental organizations that are working for the promotion of small businesses like Support and Training Entrepreneurship Programme (STEP), Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) through capacity building initiative and encouragement.

Many communities established Community Banks (CBs) which were changed to Micro Finance Banks (MFBs) from 1996 as self – sustaining financial institutions for the aim of making rural economy vibrant by providing credit facilities, deposit banking and other banking services to their customers. These MFBs also promote rural development and productive capacities of rural populace and small businesses by granting them soft loan (Eze, 2012). Despite these efforts, small manufacturing businesses are yet to impact the economy (Ogbo & Agu, 2012). This shows there is a basic issue affecting small manufacturing enterprises that has not been properly addressed.

Statement of the Problem- The small scale manufacturing sub sector is expected to contribute to economic growth of the nation through creation of jobs, raising standard of living, reducing poverty *etc*. This sub sector in Enugu East Senatorial zone is not vibrant as many of them are constantly downsizing and laying off their employees while some exit the market after few years of being in business. These enterprises are mainly managed by the owners of the businesses and it could create an elitist attitude that may affect the running of the business. The managerial functions being solely the right of one person have its advantages and disadvantages as in the case of small manufacturing enterprises. If the proprietor lacks proper managerial skills, and is a good entrepreneur, his style of management might affect the business. Thus a gap exists between the proprietor/ manager ideas of how the enterprise should be run and his abilities on one side and the real needs of the enterprise.

Research Questions i. The above problem statement triggered the following research questions

- What is the effect of poor planning on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone
- What is the effect of lack of finance on small enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone

Objectives of the Study: The main objective of this work is

- To determine the challenges and prospects of managing small manufacturing business in Enugu East Senatorial zone.

To support the main objective, the following sub objectives were identified:

- i. To ascertain the effect of poor planning on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone
- ii. To examine the effect of lack of finance on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone

Hypotheses: In line with the research questions and objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated:

- Ha i: Poor planning has positive effect on small-scale manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone.
- Ha ii: Lack of finance has positive effect on small scale manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone

II. Review of Related Literature

Definition of Small Scale Business: Scholars agree that small scale businesses have no general definition however Olatunji (2010), states that small scale business is any enterprise that its operational capital and production capacity is small and it controls small market share and has less than 50 employees. In addition all the managerial and other business functions are vested in the owner of the business.

Boswell (1978) in Eze (2012) opines that the definition of small scale enterprise by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization is the most useful and it states that a small-scale business is one that possesses two or more of the following characteristics:

- i. Ownership of the business and management are the responsibility of the same person.
- ii. The business contribution to the market is small.
- iii. The owner/manager provides the capital and makes all the policy decisions.
- iv. The operational area of the business is localized, though some may have branches outside their operational

area; but such branches are serve as depots.

- v. The owner makes day to day operational decisions and has firm control of the enterprise.

Ngwu (2014), states that each country has its own basis for defining small business, some use capital investment, while others use management structure to define small enterprise. In Nigeria, there is also no consensus definition of small enterprise. The Nigeria Bank for Commerce and Industry in its definition of small enterprise states that small enterprises are firms with assets not exceeding Seven Hundred and Fifty Thousand Naira and paid employee not above 50 persons and such a company is entirely owned by Nigerians. The National Economic Reconstruction Fund defines a small scale enterprise as a business that does not have more than Ten Million Naira capitation. This definition by National Economic Reconstruction Fund is the basis for categorizing small manufacturing enterprises in this study.

Definition of Management- Practitioners and writers have made effort to develop principles and practices of management that emphasize organizational effectiveness. Koontz (1961) in Ngwu (2014) opines that management is the ability of getting things done through people in a formal and organized group. Drucker (1985) states that management basic tasks are innovation and marketing. Ezigbo (2011) refers to management as the use of orgainsational resources to achieve organizational goal through planning, organizing, leading and controlling.

Reh (2018) opines that a manager is someone whose responsibility is to plan, direct and control the workforce in other to achieve the goals of the organization. This definition has three primary activities which are (1) the manager sets up a plan that will be followed to get the work done, (2) the manager allocates resources for the implementation of the plan, (3) the manager evaluates the result to find out if the outcome matches the stated objective. Failings of small manufacturing enterprises could be linked to lack of adequate effort any of these areas. The definition also postulates that it is the duty of the manager to evaluate the details that may not be needful currently but may be of use later. These evaluations are used to set the objectives in the planning stage. The outcome of the evaluation becomes the base for the next planning stage. Managers of small manufacturing enterprises have the duty of managing all aspects of their enterprise using the basic functions of management.

Basic Functions of Management - Management functions are often stated as planning, organizing, staffing, leading, and controlling. Ezigbo (2011) states that planning entails analysis of the situation, determining future goals, and making decision in advance on the actions that would be taken to achieve the goals of the organization. This means that in planning, the manager decides the activities that will be carried out in future which could be today, next week, next month, next year, five years, etc., and generates appropriate action.

Organising - Certo and Certo (2012) define organising as the establishment of an orderly process for the use of organizational resources. This process involves- i. Reflection on plans and objectives; ii. Establishment of major tasks; iii. Sharing the major tasks in sub tasks, iv. Assigning directives and organizational resources to subordinates and v. Evaluation of results.

Staffing - Staffing as a management function is to control all recruitment and employee needs of the organization with the aim of hiring the right people that will help the organization realize its objectives. Staffing also involves training, development; promotions, transfers and performance appraisal. (Mangaleswaran, 2015)

Leading/Directing - Leading influences employees to work in other to achieve organisational goals. Effective managers are invariably effective leaders, therefore leading entails followership and people usually align with those that satisfy their needs, wishes, and desires. This means that leading involves communication and motivation.

Controlling - Controlling involves checking progress against plans, and correcting of activities of subordinates, ensuring that work outcome conforms to plans. It also appraises performance, indicates where there are deviations, and set in motion actions that will correct deviations, and help ensure accomplishment of plans. (Ezigbo, 2011).

Types of Business Management in Small Enterprises- Managers/owners of small enterprises take responsibility of the following functions in their enterprises -

- i. Financial Management which is the responsibility of managing organizational funds in a manner that leads to achievement of organizational goals. Mensah (2011) opines that a positive relationship exists between organisational performance and the accounting information that small enterprises produce and use in their business. Therefore,

improved management of finance will assist small manufacturing enterprise owners/managers to develop their businesses. Barrow (2010) states that there is proof which points to small firms being inefficient users of working capital which makes it highly difficult to attract funds from financial institutions.

ii. Human Resource Management- Human Resource Management assists in the accomplishment of organisational objectives by making sure the organisation hires, develops, retains, terminates and uses properly the human resource in the organisation (Donnelly, Gibson & Ivancerich (1992) in Ezigbo (2011). The practice of human resource management is a very significant area that managers of small manufacturing enterprises should improve on as the organisations grow.

In many instances, the owner of a small manufacturing enterprise is responsible for the human resource functions, because these functions are usually limited when the firm employs only a few people. Obviously, there may not be need for a small manufacturing business with less than 10 employees to develop complicated human resource scheme but for businesses that are categorized as 'small' but have large population of employees, they need effective human resource policies for their workforce (Eze, 2012). However, while some small manufacturing business owners/managers consider management of human resource to be an important issue, textbooks on business management do not give enough coverage to the relevant concerns for human resource management in small enterprises (Eze, 2012).

Kok (2013) found out from his study that small firms particularly family business applies less formal human resource practices as do businesses without a business plan. Effective Human resource management enables employees to add value to the business; therefore owners/managers of small manufacturing enterprises should recognize that human resource issues can have a decisive impact on business health.

Marketing Management- Marketing management consists of the analysis, planning and decision-making that a manager carries out to implement a marketing plan that is considered to improve the development of the business (Certo and Certo, 2012). This is achieved by doing the following: i. Determining or reassessing the business's goals, ii. Preparing a business plan, iii. Designing a marketing plan iv. Writing a financial plan - forecasting, planning and budgeting.

Strategic Management- Strategic management is a process whereby senior management establishes long term direction, sets performance objectives, identifies courses of action and responses to changing business environment. In small business sector, strategies are difficult to define, what could be identified are the behaviours and actions of the owner /manager (Labontiu, 2012). Rice (2016) affirms in her study of making strategic decisions in small enterprises, that the smaller the enterprise, the more challenging it becomes to draw boundaries in the business, therefore, decision making may be more difficult in small businesses that are made up of family members. This difficulty to make strategic plans in small enterprise is interrelated with problems of management since strategy, its formulation and implementation are key management issues (Ngwu, 2014).

Operation / Production Management - Operations management is the overseeing, designing and redesigning the operations of small enterprises. It involves the duty of making sure that the little resources of small enterprises are used very well in their operations to meet customer requirements (Ngwu, 2014).

The Importance of Small Enterprise- Small scale enterprises create job opportunities for many people. Many people have been hired by small enterprises. There are a lot of small restaurant, poultry farms, cell phone repair shops, call card selling shops etc which have been established and are being managed very well by Nigerians who would have been out of job. A good number of these businesses have grown and offered employment to other unemployed people. Innocent Chukwuma, Aliko Dangote, Allen Onyema and other successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria, started their businesses on a small scale before their businesses grew into conglomerates.

Small enterprises have raised the dignity of labour. The spirit of 'I am capable ' gives people the energy to work hard, grow their businesses and finally become employers of labour. Successful small enterprises have positioned Nigerian youths as very successful business people. This is seen in the many success stories recorded by the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria.

Brief History of Small Enterprise in Nigeria- Ayozie (2011) states that evidence abounds in our respective communities of the successful stories of our great grandparents in farming, trading, iron smelting etc. So their success stories were because of their attitude to their enterprise.

The Nigerian business environment was controlled by the Colonial and Multinational Companies like Royal Niger Company, GB Olivant, Bata, Leventis, Kingsway, etc before independence. These enterprises were into trading finished goods from their parent companies in overseas. The Nigerian economy was taken by these multinational corporations because of their strong base and experience. These corporations were assisted by the government through tax concessions and other favourable policies. The educated Nigerians were not interested in business but in occupying positions in government left by the expatriates who were leaving Nigeria because of the coming independence in 1960 because they felt it was more prestigious than doing business.

An unprecedented breakthrough for small enterprises came with the indigenization Decree of 1972 and the Nigeria Enterprises Promotion Act 1977. The government since then has continued to work for the development of small enterprises through formulation of policies and establishment of agencies that could assist small scale owners like National Directorate of Employment (NDE), that assist commercial banks in disbursement of loans to small business owners, Micro Finance Banks (MFB), Trader Moni, You Win Entrepreneurship Programme, N-Power, Nigeria Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), Bank of Industry (BOI), Nigeria Export and Import Bank (NEXIM), World Bank Assisted SME II Loan Project, etc. The incorporation of entrepreneurship courses in the curricular of tertiary education is a sign of the federal government's commitment to the development of small businesses and its understanding of the importance of small enterprises' contribution to the economic development of any nation.

Effect of Small Business on the Economic Development of Nigeria- Agwu (2014) states that 80% of registered businesses in Nigeria are small and medium businesses, doing business in agro-based and allied industries like shoe production, electronics and general merchandising, hospitality and fashion industries, paint production, animal husbandry etc; and these help to advance the local man power.

Small scale business curbs urban migration: The establishment of small businesses in rural communities helps to check migration to the cities. Other noticeable effect is that small businesses facilitate the development of local entrepreneurship, for example the Innosons, Ibetos, etc started as small businesses.

Management problems - Lack of proper use of funds and management skills constitute problem to the survival of small businesses in Nigeria. West and Wood (2012) in Agwu (2014), state that 90% of business failures are as a result of lack of competence in general business management, poor keeping of financial records, misapplication of funds, and wrong decisions.

Financial problems - Small businesses have great problem with accessing of funds and credit facilities from financial institutions. Factors inhibiting funds accessibility by small businesses include strict conditions set by the financial institutions, wrong deployment of resources by owner / managers, and other conditions (West and Wood, 2012 in Agwu, 2014). Bruch and Hiemenz (2010) in Agwu (2014) observe that financing working capital needs and misapplication of funds are the most frequently mentioned financial problems of small enterprises.

Getahun (2015) conducted a study on problems of small manufacturing enterprises in Addis Ababa. The study discovered that poor management practice and capitation, lack of necessary infrastructure are the major obstacles militating against the growth of small manufacturing enterprises in Ethiopia. The study suggested the use of multi-dimensional approach in tackling these challenges.

III. Methodology

The study adopted the survey design. The population consists of thirty-nine (39) employees and management in specific small manufacturing businesses (vegetable oil and paint manufacturing) which were purposely selected and considered to be the sample. The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire (on a five-point Likert scale). Opinion of experts were sought to ensure face and content validity of the research instrument. The outcome was subjected to reliability test using Cronbach Alpha technique which yielded a correlation co-efficient of 0.89 indicating a high degree of item consistency. The hypotheses were tested with ordinal logistic regression using SPSS (v.20).

IV. Results

Objective 1: To ascertain the effect of poor planning on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone.

Table 1: Analysis of the effect of poor planning on small manufacturing enterprises.

S/N	To ascertain the effect of poor planning on small manufacturing businesses.	SA	A	U	SD	D	Total (%)
(i)	Lack of budgeting affects the day to day running of small manufacturing business	14 (36%)	9 (23%)	5 (13%)	7 (18%)	4 (10%)	39 (100%)
(ii)	Lack of strengths and weaknesses consideration is a major obstacle in small manufacturing business	28 (72%)	11 (28%)	0	0	0	39 (100%)
(iii)	Lack of clear administrative structure is a problem for small manufacturing business	18 (46%)	6 (15%)	4 (10%)	2 (5%)	9 (23%)	39 (100%)
(iv)	The owner being manager is a major management problem in small manufacturing business	11 (28%)	5 (13%)	8 (21%)	9 (23%)	6 (15%)	39 (100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2018.

Table 1 shows that twenty-three respondents representing (59%) accept that lack of budgeting affects the day to day running of small manufacturing businesses, five respondents representing (13%) were undecided while eleven (28%) respondents disagree that budgetary planning infringes on day-to-day running of small manufacturing business. Thirty-nine respondents representing (100%) accepted that failure to carry out strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threat (SWOT) analyses before delving into small manufacturing enterprise affect the business. Furthermore, results also showed that twenty-four respondents representing (61%) agreed that lack of clear administrative structure is a problem for small manufacturing enterprise; four respondents representing (10%) were undecided while eleven respondents (28%) had a contrary opinion. Lastly, sixteen respondents (41%) concurred that owner related management problem adversely affect small manufacturing business, eight respondents constituting (21%) were neutral while fifteen respondents representing (38%) disagreed with the statement. Inductively, it is evident that lack of poor planning exerts adverse effect on small manufacturing enterprises.

Table 2: Ordinal Logistic Regression Test Result for Hypothesis (1)

H₁: Poor planning has positive effect on small-scale manufacturing business in Enugu East Senatorial zone.
Parameter Estimates

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold [SMEs = 17]	1.312	11.052	0.115	1	.021	1.312	1.417
Location [Poor_Planning = 5]	-3.109	1.250	0.414	1	.002	-3.109	-4.259

Link function: Logit.

The result in Table 2 shows that poor planning has negative effect on small scale manufacturing enterprises with a decrease in the probability of increased business at an odds ratio of -3.109 (95% CI, -3.109 to -4.259), Wald $\chi^2(1) = 0.115$, $p < 0.002$ ($p = 0.002$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis which states that poor planning positively affects small scale businesses in Enugu East Senatorial zone is hereby rejected and the null hypothesis accepted.

Objective 2: To examine the effect of lack of finance on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu-east senatorial zone.

Table 3: Analysis of the effect of lack of finance on small manufacturing enterprises

S/N	To examine the effect of lack of finance on small manufacturing businesses.	SA	A	U	SD	D	Total (%)
(i)	Lack of collateral for obtaining loan financing make business expansion an impossible task for small manufacturing business.	14 (36%)	9 (23%)	3 (8%)	6 (15%)	7 (18%)	39 (100%)
(ii)	Funding from family and friends is inadequate for rapid growth of small manufacturing business.	25 (64%)	14 (36%)	0	0	0	39 (100%)
(iii)	Poor access to loan financing from commercial banks expose small manufacturing businesses to loan sharks.	17 (44%)	13 (33%)	0	1 (3%)	8 (21%)	39 (100%)
(iv)	Insufficient funding impacts negatively on small manufacturing enterprises.	22 (56%)	10 (26%)	1 (3%)	0	6 (15%)	39 (100%)

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 3 indicates that twenty-three respondents representing (59%) accepted that lack of collateral for obtaining loan financing make business expansion an impossible task for small manufacturing businesses, three respondents representing (8%) were undecided while thirteen respondents representing (33%) disagreed. Also, thirty-nine respondents representing (100%) agreed that funding received from family and friends is inadequate for rapid growth of small manufacturing enterprises. Furthermore, thirty respondents representing (77%) agreed that poor access to loan financing from commercial banks expose small manufacturing businesses to loan sharks while nine respondents representing (24%) disagreed. Finally, thirty-two respondents (82%) affirmed that insufficient funding generally impacts negatively on small manufacturing enterprises. Thus, it is evident that lack of finance is a major draw-back to the growth of small scale manufacturing businesses in the study area.

Table 4: Ordinal Logistic Regression Test Result for Hypothesis (2)

H₂: Lack of finance has positive effect on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone

Parameter Estimates

	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold [SMEs = 3]	1.072	11.131	0.219	1	.005	1.072	1.156
Location [Lack_of_Finance = 13]	-5.937	13.250	1.785	1	.023	-5.937	-6.152

Link function: Logit.

The result in Table 4 shows that poor planning has negative effect on small scale manufacturing business with a decrease in the probability of increased business at an odds ratio of -3.109 (95% CI, -5.937 to -6.152), Wald χ^2 (1) = 1.785, $p < 0.023$ ($p = 0.023$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis which states that poor planning positively affects small manufacturing businesses in Enugu East Senatorial zone is hereby rejected and the null hypothesis accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The study ascertained the effect of poor planning on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone. The result from ordinal logistic regression test revealed that poor planning has negative effect on small scale manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone (Estimate = -3.109, Wald = 0.414, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$). Thus, the alternate hypothesis which states that poor planning has positive effect on small-scale manufacturing business is rejected and the null hypothesis accepted. This indicates that deliberate and adequate planning is an integral part of

success in small scale enterprises. Egbuna and Agali, (2013) established that proper planning can increase the productivity and profitability of small and medium scale enterprises.

The study also examined the effect of lack of finance on small manufacturing enterprises in the study area. . The result from ordinal logistic regression test revealed that lack of finance impacts negatively on small scale manufacturing enterprises in the study area. (Estimate = -5.937, Wald = 1.785, P = 0.023 < 0.05). Hence, the alternate hypothesis which states that lack of finance has positive effect on small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone is rejected and the null accepted. This implies that lack of finance is a major challenge facing small manufacturing enterprises in Enugu East Senatorial zone.

This study has also validated the work of some earlier researchers such as Alabi, Awe and Musa (2015) who established that adequate finance is indispensable for the successful operation of small and medium enterprises, Egbuna and Agali (2013) posit that economic instability and access to source of finance are major challenges facing Small and Medium Enterprises.

The study therefore concluded that if managers/owners understand that managing a business is different from owning a business, and draws a distinct boundary between the business and themselves and if the enterprise gets adequate financial support, the rate of small manufacturing business failure would reduce and their prospects which include job creation, reduction in poverty, rural development, improvement of living standards will be achieved.

The study recommended that government, non – governmental organizations should be organizing periodic training for small scale business owners/managers. This should be a platform to educate them on how to manage, promote and develop their businesses in order to advance economic development in Nigeria. Financial institutions should be encouraged to give credit to small entrepreneurs at low rate. This study has contributed to widening the scope of literature in this area of small business management. It brings in current data and analyses, thus providing current information that is relevant to scholars interested in Nigeria.

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